

On a New Series of Double Sulphates of the Copper- Magnesium Group and the Sulphonium Bases. Part I.

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Sulphonium compounds have long been known. The starting point of preparing the various sulphonium compounds is generally the sulphonium iodide which is obtained by the condensation of a sulphide with an alkyl iodide. Thus triethyl sulphonium iodide is obtained according to the reaction,

By far the more important compound of this class is the hydroxide which is obtained by treatment of the iodide with moist silver oxide. The sulphonium hydroxides have been found to be strong bases and are comparable to the hydroxides of the alkali metals, the heats of neutralisation and other physico-chemical data of these two classes of bases being very nearly the same. It thus appears that the corresponding salts of the sulphonium compounds will be well-defined crystalline salts and will behave similarly to the salts of the alkali metals. Now, it is a well known fact that the simple salts of the alkali metals form double salts with the salts of various metals such as mercury, gold, platinum, cadmium, iron, copper, etc. The sulphonium salts are, therefore, likely to produce such double salts. In fact Stromholm (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2283) has obtained double salts of sulphonium chlorides with mercuric chloride. Klinger and Massen have obtained double salts of sulphonium chlorides and iodides with iodides of cadmium, mercury, platinum, gold, tin and arsenic. (*Annalen*, 1888, 243, 193; 1889, 252, 241). Blattler (*Monatsh.*, 1919, 40, 417) has obtained double salts of trimethyl sulphonium halides with metallic halides.

Uptil now no double sulphate has been obtained from the sulphonium sulphates and other metallic sulphates. It is well known that

sulphates of certain bivalent metals yield, as a rule, with alkali sulphates as also with the sulphate of ammonia, double salts of the type,

$M'' = \text{Fe (ous), Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Mg, Cu, Cd, etc.,}$

and $M' = \text{K, Na, (NH}_4\text{), etc.}$

Sulphates derived from strong organic bases are also known to form double salts with these metallic sulphates and are either exactly or very similar to the type mentioned. Thus Grossman and Schuck (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 27; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1906, II, 1048, 1243) describe a double sulphate of ethylamine sulphate and zinc sulphate, $(C_2H_5NH_2)_2H_2SO_4 \cdot ZnSO_4 \cdot 8H_2O$ and Grossman, Schuck and Steinmetz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 29; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1906, II, 1048, 1243) described the double salt $(CH_3NH_2)_2SO_4 \cdot ZnSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$. With ethylene diammonium sulphates of the above bivalent metals Grossman and Schuck (*loc. cit.*) have also obtained double sulphates containing four, six, and eight molecules of water of crystallisation. Recently similar double sulphates have been obtained by Canneri (*Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 611) from guanidine sulphate and these metallic sulphates in which case the salts are of the type $M''SO_4 \cdot M'SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$. In all these double salts it is found that the organic sulphates behave like sulphates of the alkali metals. It was, therefore, expected that sulphonium sulphates will also behave similarly. Consequently it was found desirable to study the interaction of the sulphates of the sulphonium bases with the vitriolic sulphates.

The expectation has been only partially realised. Double sulphates of triethyl sulphonium sulphate and the vitriolic sulphates have been obtained with this difference that instead of being hexa-hydrated as was anticipated from the close analogy of the sulphonium compounds with those of the alkali metals, they are invariably deca-hydrated. The behaviour of manganese and magnesium has been, however, found to be rather anomalous, as the double salts, which they yield, conform to the formula $2 M''SO_4 \cdot M'SO_4 \cdot 11H_2O$. Double sulphates of manganese and ammonium (Lepierre, *Compt. rend.*, 1895, 120, 924; *Bull. Soc. Chim.* 1895, [iii] 13, 595; Schreinemakers, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1909, 6, 131), manganese and potassium (Mallet, *Chem. News*, 1899, 80, 300) and also of magnesium and potassium (Precht, *Chem. Industrie*, 1880, 3, 418)

and of magnesium and sodium (Chatelier, *Compt. rend.*, 1896, 123, 746) of the type $2M''SO_4, M'SO_4$, have been described but they contain no water of crystallisation, whereas those which form the subject of the present investigation contain eleven molecules of water.

Sulphonium sulphates have not yet been isolated and in the present case it has been found that on neutralising the triethyl sulphonium hydroxide with sulphuric acid, the sulphate can be obtained in solution only. On being concentrated and finally evaporated to dryness in a vacuum it solidifies to a transparent glassy mass, which on being exposed to the moist atmosphere absorbs moisture and in a few minutes goes into solution. It was thus too hygroscopic to admit of direct weighing. It was also soluble in alcohol, as is expected in the case of an organic sulphate. In these respects, therefore, the sulphonium sulphates behave differently from the sulphates of the alkali metals. The strong affinity of the sulphonium compounds for water, exhibited by their hygroscopic nature, seem to be satisfied by a large water content of the molecule of the derived double sulphates.

These double sulphates are hygroscopic and crystallise in needles. They are readily soluble in water and when their concentrated aqueous solutions are treated with alcohol, the inorganic components alone separate out. On heating on a platinum spatula, the substances melt in the water of crystallisation and afterwards decompose with charring; the organic sulphur component is found to burn on the spatula and a smell of ethyl sulphide is distinctly perceptible.

One remarkable behaviour was observed when, in the case of nickel, methyl sulphonium sulphate was substituted for the corresponding ethyl derivative. The double salt obtained had the formula $2NiSO_4, [(CH_3)_3S], SO_4, 11H_2O$, that is, it behaved like manganese and magnesium sulphates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Triethyl Sulphonium Sulphate.

The method given by Oefele (*Annalen*, 1865, 132, 82) for the preparation of the iodide is lacking in detail. The following procedure gave satisfactory results.

Thirty two g. of ethyl iodide and 18 g. of ethyl sulphide with 10 c.c. of water were heated under reflux on a water bath for 15 to

20 hours till a homogeneous solution was obtained. The solution which was coloured by the liberated iodine was allowed to evaporate spontaneously in a vacuum, when colourless rhombic plates of triethyl sulphonium iodide crystallised out in two or three days (yield about 40 g.). The iodide may be purified by recrystallisation from hot anhydrous alcohol or from a mixture of anhydrous alcohol and ether.

The iodide was then converted into the hydroxide by rubbing with excess of silver oxide in presence of water. The solution was filtered, the filtrate neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid and concentrated somewhat on the water-bath. As it cannot be isolated, the preparations of the double salts had to be undertaken with the sulphonium sulphate in solution.

General Method for the Preparation of the Double Sulphates.

Considerable difficulty was experienced in preparing the double salts. The reactant sulphates were at first mixed in molecular proportions, the amount of the sulphonium sulphate being calculated from the amount of the iodide taken, and the solution was allowed to evaporate spontaneously over sulphuric acid in a vacuum. It was noticed, however, that under these conditions successive crops of the vitriolic sulphate alone crystallised out in the pure state. In one or two cases only, it was found that after a few crops of the pure vitriolic sulphate had crystallised out and the mother-liquor had become sufficiently rich in the sulphonium compound, the double salts began to put in an appearance. On using the metallic sulphates and the organic sulphate in the ratio of 1:2, the desired results were most strikingly secured. The double salts began to crystallise from the very beginning and in no case was any previous separation of the pure metallic sulphate observed. This peculiar behaviour was noticed even in the cases of manganese and magnesium compounds, where the metallic sulphates and the organic sulphate exist in the ratio of 2:1.

During crystallisation the mother-liquor assumed a thick syrupy state. The crystals of the double sulphates were drained free from the mother-liquor and dried by pressing between folds of a filter paper and analysed. The double salts are deliquescent and consequently unnecessary exposure to the atmosphere has to be carefully avoided.

In the preparation of nickel trimethyl sulphonium sulphate the proportion of the components used above and the procedure adopted were also the same.

Successive crops of the same preparation were collected in each case and found on analysis to give identical results.

Ferrous triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

It crystallised in long, white needles from solution, which was coloured red owing to slight decomposition. The crystals too decomposed in a day or two giving out ethyl sulphide. (Found : Fe, 8.35; C, 20.71*; H, 7.53; SO₄, 28.45. FeSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 10H₂O requires Fe, 8.38; C, 21.61; H, 7.56; SO₄, 28.88 per cent.).

Zinc triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

The double salt was obtained in white needle-shaped crystals. It is fairly stable in a dry atmosphere. (Found : Zn, 9.68; SO₄, 29.19. ZnSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 10H₂O requires Zn, 9.67; SO₄, 28.42 per cent.).

Nickel triethyl sulphonium sulphate crystallised in long, greenish needles which are fairly stable. (Found : Ni, 8.71; SO₄, 29.01. NiSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 10H₂O requires Ni, 8.77; SO₄, 28.70 per cent.).

Cobalt triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

The crystals obtained were coloured pink. (Found : Co, 8.86; SO₄, 29.32; CoSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 10H₂O requires Co, 8.80; SO₄, 28.69 per cent.).

Cadmium triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

The substance was obtained in white needle-shaped crystals. (Found : Cd, 15.39; SO₄, 27.68. CdSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 10H₂O requires Cd, 15.56; SO₄, 26.57 per cent.).

Magnesium triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

It crystallised in long white needles. (Found : Mg, 6.37; SO₄, 37.40; C, 17.86*; H, 6.74. 2MgSO₄[(C₂H₅)₃S]₂SO₄ · 11H₂O requires Mg, 6.26; SO₄, 37.27; C, 18.63; H, 6.79 per cent.).

* Owing to the volatile nature of ethyl sulphide and sudden decomposition of the double sulphates during combustion, traces of the former escape un-oxidised, hence the carbon often comes out slightly low.

Manganese triethyl sulphonium sulphate.

The double salt was obtained in the shape of slightly pink-coloured crystals. (Found: Mn, 18.00; SO₄, 35.01. 2MnSO₄. [(C₂H₅)₃S], SO₄. 11H₂O requires Mn, 18.16; SO₄, 34.58 per cent.).

Nickel trimethyl sulphonium sulphate.

The double salt was obtained as green crystals. (Found: Ni, 15.62; SO₄, 37.74. 2NiSO₄[(CH₃)₃S]₂SO₄. 11H₂O requires Ni, 15.48; SO₄, 38.02 per cent.).

The Compound of Triethyl Sulphonium Sulphate and Copper Sulphate.

The behaviour of copper sulphate with triethyl sulphonium sulphate was also studied. The sulphate solutions were mixed in the usual proportion and allowed to crystallise. After many days the blue solution assumed a very thick syrupy state from which after a further lapse of several days, bluish white, fine, silky needles began to separate out. The crystallisation was very slow and it was found extremely difficult to completely free the crystals from the adhering mother-liquor. Since sufficient amount could not be collected for analysis the composition was not determined. The small amount collected was very moist. On being preserved in a desiccator for a few days, it turned green. The blue compound could, however, be reproduced on exposure of the green compound to the moist atmosphere. A portion of the substance was held in a non-luminous flame on a platinum spatula and it was found to burn giving out a distinct smell of ethyl sulphide. This test suggests the formation of a true compound of triethyl sulphonium sulphate and copper sulphate.

Further investigation is in progress especially in the direction of the effect of substitution of ethyl by one or more of alkyl radicles like methyl, propyl, butyl, etc., on the composition of the resulting double salts.

In conclusion we beg to express our sincere thanks to Mr. Kshitish Chandra Bose-Rây for his ungrudging help in conducting some of the experimental work in connection with the investigation.